

Promoting learners' voice productions with a chatbot as a tool for improving the learning process in a MOOC

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Abstract

The adoption of mobile devices in the learning process shows positive effects. One of the fields of research that has yielded positive results of using m-learning techniques is the peer to peer (p2p) evaluation. Although globally widespread instant messaging (IM) mobile applications such as the WhatsApp or Telegram were not originally designed as educational tools, they have been repurposed as platforms for p2p use. The IM applications are augmented by offering "chatbots" or "bots" for their users. These virtual assistant bots assist students by offering them a multitude of services in the form of text or voice dialogs. This work proposes a new method for integrating p2p essays' evaluation using voice recordings with the help of a chatbot. We argue that using this system we can effectively improve both the typical learning and the p2p evaluation process of a MOOC essay. We performed a two-month experiment with 77 participants that recorded 737 voice answers with a Telegram based chatbot. We describe in detail how to use a chatbot as a means to perform a new kind of assignment in a MOOC, and how to design voice-based challenges based on the results of our experiment, where 90% of the learners stated that they would like to use this kind of chatbots in new future courses.

Keywords: MOOC, chatbots, Telegram, p2p assessments, mobile learning, voice-recordings

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1. Introduction

Since the "Connectivism and Connective Knowledge" course organized by George Siemens and Stephen Downes at the University of Manitoba (Canada) in August 2008 through November 2012, to when The New York Times published, "The Year of the MOOC" (Pappano, 2012) the MOOC phenomenon (Massive Open Online Courses) has become a forceful idea within the educational community (Regalado, 2012). During this period there was a proliferation of courses of all kinds offered, which promised the democratization of education, while suggesting the possibility of learning from the best (Dalipi, Imran, Idrizi & Aliu, 2017). MOOCs went from being a collaborative tool of specific users to becoming known and used by the general public.

This online learning model was established and continues to evolve, and shows the following basic characteristics: the number of sites is unlimited, anyone can register, it promotes the autonomous and active learning of students, resources— whether videos, articles, infographics or discussion forums, are available via the Internet (Chen, 2011; Lee & Lehto, 2013), some web browsing device is used (Pimmer, Mateescu & Grhbiel, 2016), and it can be accessed anywhere at any time (Briz-Ponce, Pereira, Carvalho, Juanes-Mndez & Garca-Pealvo, 2016).

In recent years, numerous classifications on MOOCs have emerged (Snchez-Gordn & Lujn-Mora, 2014). For the purpose of this study, it is enough to refer to the proposal based on George Siemens (Siemens, 2012) ideology:

- *The cMOOC model*: Courses follow the Connectivist learning philosophy of open and participatory oriented learning based on communities of students and teachers where the students self-manage and knowledge is created through establishing connections. The greater the number of connections, the bigger the learning potential. Participants are encouraged to contribute their own experiences to the learning sessions.
- *The xMOOC model*: Is content-based, and is a more traditional approach,

generally supported by large and well-funded universities. xMoocs follow
30 a curriculum and communications pattern similar to curriculum centric
classroom teaching.

The sMOOC (Social MOOC) model appears later on and, like cMOOC, it
emphasises the role of students and the interactions among them (Miyazoe &
Anderson, 2013). The sMOOC model prioritizes collaborative interactions on-
35 line just like cMOOC, but also takes from xMOOCs more traditional design.
It promotes a certain directionality towards a more engaged participation by
teachers and the use of high-quality content, relevant web resources or pre-
established content units (Yousef, Chatti, Wosnitza & Schroeder, 2015). To
carry out a social interaction and enhance students engagement in their learn-
40 ing, the sMOOC model takes a further step in continuity and transference of
learning. The sMOOC model suggests accessibility to different platforms and
mobile devices as well as the integration of participants in real-life experiences by
contextualizing content. Therefore, working with apps, social media immersion
and gamification strategies are possible.

45 In a classical instructional-design, a MOOC proposes activities aimed at
evaluating students' learning in different ways and with different purposes (self-
assessment, automatic evaluation, peer-review or P2P and collaborative assess-
ment) (Torres-Mancera & Gago-Saldae, 2014). However, there are doubts about
which assessment system are most appropriate in this type of course (Acosta &
50 Otero, 2014). Peer-review or P2P assessment is the main element in these evalu-
ation activities in the MOOCs (Torres-Mancera & Gago-Saldae, 2014). Through
this method of peer evaluation, well-known among the academic community as
a way of improving the knowledge base, the classmates of the course are given
the role of "expert" and they determine the quality of the work presented by
55 other students. The quality scales are specified in a rubric that indicates the
evaluated criteria and the value that is granted to them according to the execu-
tion of each of the sections. This rubric will make the work as evaluator easier
for the students and invites them to reflect on the value of their own work.

The learners are responsible for their own learning through practice. Different
60 authors support the benefit of a P2P assessment for both teachers and learners
(Al-Imari, Yang & Pimlott, 2016; Maiti, Kist & Maxwell, 2014; Matsuo, Barolli,
Arnedo-Moreno, Xhafa, Koyama & Durrezi, 2009).

But is enough time devoted to P2P testing instruction, which is central to
MOOC evaluations? One of the worries when applying peer-assessment is the
65 possibility of students making mistakes in evaluation as they are inexperienced
(Sluijsmans (2002)). Peer assessment needs training and practice, arguably on
neutral products or performances, before full implementation (Topping (2003)).
Indeed, the skill to assess the work of peers is not present for granted. It should
be taught. As Sluijsmans, Brand-Gruwel, van Merrinboer & Martens (2004)
70 describe, there are specific programs for training student teachers candidates on
this important skill (in how to make critical judgements about the performance
of peers).

Do learners get enough training before they have to tackle it? Instruction is
understood as the teaching in the concepts and procedures necessary to effec-
75 tively carry out this evaluation practice. Generally, students are reluctant to do
this type of written testing and for that reason studies reveal that students are
much more comfortable with evaluation systems based on automatisms. When
an instrument of evaluation between pairs is introduced, there are many stu-
dents that decide to leave the MOOC (Acosta & Otero, 2014; Peterson, 2013).
80 One of the possible reasons for this disengagement may be based in outdated
tooling. There is a growing gap between the tools students use on a day-to-day
basis and those used for the P2P evaluation and in written tests. Students
are accustomed to using mobile devices, multimedia tools (video, audio, voice,
graphics ...) and instant communication systems (WhatsApp, Telegram, Face-
85 book Messenger). The P2P tests of written works used so far in MOOC courses
lack this interactivity. This research presents an experience that combines the
use of smartphones, instant messaging (based on chatbots) and voice recordings
to create a system that allows the evaluation of P2P works, motivates students
and integrates the way that they use technologies.

90 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First (Section 2), we describe some previous work in the integration of voice recordings in education, especially in the p2p evaluation area, and some previous experiments using chatbots in the education area. In Section 3, we detail the context of our experiment, and how it is applied to a custom-built chatbot system to perform
95 p2p evaluated voice-exercises to our MOOC. Section 4 is devoted to show the results of our work, both in quantitative terms (number of voice recordings, duration, number of evaluations received...) and in qualitative terms (opinions that our students expressed in a survey). The results are discussed in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6 we propose some conclusions that could be applied by
100 other MOOC practitioners.

2. Related Work

In spite of the above problems, there is an increase in the use of peer evaluation in online learning environments. A systematic review found "evidence of an improvement in student performance when using peer review system in 60% of
105 the articles" (Tenrio, Bittencourt, Isotani & Silva, 2016). It also "helps the work of teachers in at least 34.09% of the evaluated articles". On the other hand, the review shows that in almost 30% of the articles there were difficulties in the implementation of P2P techniques, mostly related to students' low motivation and dissatisfaction. Most of the P2P are based on traditional written productions
110 (Sadler & Good, 2006; Tenrio, Bittencourt, Isotani & Silva, 2016). It does not take advantage of the possibilities offered by multi-media digital tools, which have been introduced in our current everyday communication process and which can favor the ease of use perception (Pengnate & Sarathy, 2017), a key aspect in the continuity of students, especially in the MOOCs (Eranksi & Moudgalya,
115 2016). When we talk about digital multimedia tools, mobile devices, especially smartphones, dominate sales and Internet access market (Dalipi, Imran, Idrizi & Aliu, 2017). More than two-thirds of the world's population is covered by mobile broadband networks (Sanou, 2016). The number of mobile subscrip-

tions has surpassed 7.5 billion, 55% of that for smartphones. It is estimated
120 that in 2022 there will be 8.9 billion subscriptions, of which 90% will be mobile
broadband (Cerwall & Lundvall, 2016). The pervasiveness of mobile devices
and their inclusion in our socio-cultural practices is evident. It has broken the
barriers of space and time and has favored horizontal communication between
individuals (Briz-Ponce & Juanes-Mndez, 2015; Briz-Ponce, Pereira, Carvalho,
125 Juanes-Mndez & Garca-Pealvo, 2016; So, 2016). Communication and educa-
tion are closely linked and both terms have unbreakable bonds turned into a
mutually supportive binomial. In the digital age, it is not possible to conceive
learning in a non-collaborative way or another communicative model that is not
horizontal in educational settings. Consequently, mobile or ubiquitous learn-
130 ing becomes a mainstay of educommunication and a target of study to optimize
not only technology but also to delve into best practices in m-learning method-
ology, pedagogy and philosophy (Kim, Yang, Bae, Min, Lee & Kim, 2017).
The adoption of mobile devices in the learning process shows positive effects
(Pimmer et al., 2016). According to UNESCO, it favors contextualization and
135 customization, the creation of apprenticeship communities and offers immediate
feedback (West & Vosloo, 2013). One of the fields of research that has yielded
positive results is its use in peer evaluation. The so-called mobile based peer as-
sessment (MBPA) (Chao, Lan, Kinshuk & Sung, 2014; Karadeniz, 2009; Nikou
& Economides, 2017) or mobile peer assessment with augmented reality (Chen,
140 2010; Kuo, Chen, Chu, Yang & Chen, 2017).

Even globally widespread instant messaging (IM) applications such as What-
sApp or Telegram which were not designed as educational tools, have been ex-
ploited for P2P use (Guler, 2017; Tarighat & Khodabakhsh, 2016) and the term
WhatsLearn is already being spoken of (So, 2016). These practices seek to en-
145 courage student engagement and motivation. And also, the IM applications
themselves are updated by offering useful tools for their users that allow not
only maintaining market share but extending it. Chatbots or bots are one of
the main bets to get users hooked, offering them a multitude of services in the
form of virtual assistants, without abandoning the tool. A chatbot is a soft-

ware agent that can engage in a conversation with one or more humans. The conversation can be in the form of text messages, voice or a combination of both.

Even though using chatbots in education is not a new topic, what is a fresh approach is to integrate those chatbots in the IM mobile application that the learners are using on a daily basis. For example, due to its novelty (Telegram started to offer a bot API in June 2015) using a Telegram bot to implement new user interfaces and applications are scarcely documented. Ustalov (2015) developed an instant messaging Telegram bot designed for facilitating crowd annotation. Using the bot a crowd-sourced worker requests a task, submits an answer (annotation) and gets new tasks. The use of the Telegram bot facilitates the interaction of the users with the annotation service using a clean interface from their smartphones. Graf, Krger, Mller, Ruhland & Zech (2015) introduced Nombot, a Telegram bot to simplify food tracking. This bot communicates with the user and collects data about the nutrition of its chat partners. Hafiz bin Ismail bin Ismail (2015) proposes as an outline of future work an implementation of automated Telegram Bot, which would enable learners to check their grades or marks through Telegram without properly logging into their LMS. Pereira (2016) shows another e-learning related usage of Telegram chatbots, documenting the benefits (ubiquity, instant feedback, engagement) of implementing a multiple-choice quizzing application in a university grade. All in all, as we can see, there is a clear need for new articles that relate the education and chatbots world and details the e-learning positive outcomes that this union could yield.

The purpose of the present research is to introduce the use of chatbots with voice messages as a strategy that aims to increase motivation and active participation of users of a MOOC using an automated chat tool. A new innovative and creative model must be developed in order to attract the attention of today's students, since they have developed a different cognitive learning pattern due to their frequent use of digital gadgets (Lin, Yong, Fiona & Amin, 2011).

These points (motivation and active participation) are two of the five main difficulties faced by MOOCs from the onset: (1) high dropout rate (gradual

decline in participation) (Pursel, Zhang, Jablokow, Choi & Velegol, 2016), (2) lack of contextualization (Phan, McNeil & Robin, 2016), (3) dependence on student motivation (Barak, Watted & Haick, 2016) (4) reliability of evaluation processes in terms of subjectivity and plagiarism (Shi, Sun & Liu, 2016), as
185 well as (5) difficulty in tutoring and certifying what has been learned, both in knowledge and skills (MacKay, Langford & Waran, 2016).

The role of emotions in education like figuring out what motivates and engages individual students, is essential. It is the prerequisite for implementing student-centered approaches to learning. Toshalis & Nakkula (2012) observed
190 that for increasing motivation and engagement, customized teaching approaches that differentiate instruction for each student tend to work far better than one-size-fits-all techniques. Chatbots can effectively help with this personalization, administering each student a different exercise, based on their previous works and achievements. Similarly, Toshalis & Nakkula (2012) also stated that young
195 people are likely to be more motivated and engaged in an activity when they feel they have a voice in how it is conducted and can affect how it concludes. Peer assessment is certainly a tool that can be used with that purpose.

One approach to the problem of low student motivation is to use technology-based resources to spark students interest in learning. However, the evidence
200 surrounding the effectiveness of using it to ignite student interest in the academic content is sparse (Chao et al. (2016); Chen et al. (2014); Moos & Marroquin (2010)). Our experiment with chatbots, voice based exercises and mobile phones, tries to contribute some evidence to this area.

3. Material and Methods

205 Our analysis is based on the results obtained in the "sMOOC [name masked for blind review]"¹ where the use of chatbot and voice message integration of the Telegram app as an innovative tool for the implementation of the P2P eval-

¹<https://masked/course/masked-for-blind-review/>

uation. Participants responded to a set of questions posed by the bot, orally - using voice recordings - to be evaluated by peers. Voice productions can offer a
210 sense of closeness compared to written productions (Imran & Kowalski, 2014). Participants feel a closer presence of others and that increased the sense of belonging to an online learning community (Suanpang & Kalceff, 2004). It's more personal. This practice sought to train the participants in the P2P evaluation, which they would face at the end of the course in order to complete it.

215 Another element that has played an important role in this strategy to increase the low motivation and participation of the trainees (Zhang, 2016) is the use of gamification features. Miguel Scholar, a fictitious character with whom the participants had to collaborate in this activity, acted as a person and gave life to the chatbot. He proposed problems related to the implementation of
220 MOOC courses at his university to be solved by the participants. The visual representation of this avatar accompanied by different emoticons was introduced from the beginning to offer closeness and allow the identification with this character to which the students had to help. Every week this figure presented a challenge, "mission" to overcome through voice recordings using the Telegram
225 application. The avatar provided immediate feedback, showing appreciation for the answers and simulating learning through the learner's collaboration, in order to increase motivation and improve results, as suggested by Dominguez (Dominguez, Saenz-de Navarrete, de Marcos, Fernandez-Sanz, Pags & Martinez-Herriz, 2013; Leony, Munoz-Merino, Ruiperez-Valiente, Pardo & Delgado Kloos, 2015).

230 Once the responses were collected, the chatbot distributed them pseudo-randomly to be evaluated by their peers, as described in more detail in the next section.

3.1. Context

The context of our experiment is focused on two main ingredients: a MOOC
235 and a chatbot.

3.1.1. *The MOOC*

The sMOOC [name masked for blind review] is a course developed as part of European [name masked] Project, framed in the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme. It is a sMOOC simultaneously taught in six languages, with the participation of 10 European Universities and Higher Education institutions from seven European countries. The sMOOC was coordinated by [location masked for blind review] and [location masked for blind review], and aimed to train e-teachers who should be self-sufficient, critical and capable of creating their own MOOC. Once the course was passed, [name masked] Project would provide them with virtual space on its platform, where they could create their own sMOOC for free, assisted at all times by a tutor purposely assigned by [name masked] project.

A multidisciplinary team has developed the course from their professional experience and using a methodology which follows on a pedagogical approach based on social constructivism. Both individual and team work are promoted. The teaching-learning process is based on multi-format learning materials (video, audio and texts), while a wide range of resources are provided on the platform (forum boards, groups, microblogging, peer-to-peer assessment and tests) in addition to activities launched on Facebook and Twitter. The course activities foster participation among students and promote a shared social interaction.

By the end of the course, participants should be able to answer the following questions: Why do a MOOC? How is a sMOOC built? How is a sMOOC designed? What is a sMOOC based on? How can one make a sMOOC accessible and successful? How is a sMOOC assessed and its data used?

The theoretical bases for sMOOC are interculturality and inter creativity. Hence, participants are shown an educational model which shows how to teach and learn through creative and innovative interaction based in cultural exchange.

Based on those two foundations, RetosMOOCsBot (ChallengesMOOCsBot, a Telegram bot) activity is proposed. This forms a pilot experience launched only in Spanish as an experimental activity, intending to extrapolate results to

the other five languages, once the experience is studied.

Six challenges have been launched on Telegram’s chatbot, integrating specific content of the ”sMOOC [name masked for blind review]”. These six challenges were presented to participants by the avatar Becario Miguel (Intern student or Miguel the scholar), which performed as a line of work and accompanied participants throughout the entire experience. At the end of the sixth challenge, an anonymous satisfaction questionnaire was integrated, in order to provide a qualitative dimension to the research.

3.1.2. *The chatbot*

Using the API provided by the IM application Telegram we developed a chatbot that can interact in a conversation with the learner. As Fig. 1 shows, the bot includes text, graphics and voice elements. Learners had to answer text based questions proposed by the bot. For gamification and personalization reasons, the bot was playing the role of Miguel, a scholar that explained his doubts to the learners and encourage them to answer by at most, 1 minute long voice recordings. This Miguel character was also the one that assigned the recordings to the evaluators and the one that reminded them to fulfill the evaluation in case of delays.

3.2. *Technical architecture of our chatbot solution*

For this experiment a Telegram based custom chatbot system was created. The chatbot was entirely programmed for use in this course, although the source code was made available under an open source license to any interested stakeholder ². The following picture (Fig. 2) shows the technical architecture of our solution.

The picture is divided in three main blocks: users interacting with the chatbot using their smartphones, Telegram system and the SMOOC server. First, users of the chatbot will start a new voice challenge sending the /challengeX

²<https://github.com/hidden/for/blind/review>

command to our chatbot ((@retosmooocsbot). We had 6 challenges, thus the X in /challengeX command should be an integer between 1 and 6. After receiving
295 the command, our bot will ask the user some questions that they have to answer using short voice messages (it is suggested that messages should not last more than 1 minute). The Telegram system will record users voice-messages for some days. After that, the voice messages may be deleted, so Telegram suggests that chatbots should periodically download a copy of that recordings and keep
300 them in private servers. Accordingly, our bot had to periodically download voice files from Telegram and save locally, annotating in a voice cache database some metadata about each recording (who was the recorder, when was it recorded, duration, filesystem path, etc.) After enough recordings were saved, our bot had to execute an assignment script to randomly assign evaluators to each recording.
305 ing. After the assignment, the bot would periodically execute a task to notify the evaluators about pending recordings to be evaluated. We found that the evaluators sometimes needed reminders about their pending assignments. For evaluation purposes, we programmed an /evaluate command. This command shows the evaluator his/her pending voice-recording assignments. After listening to each one, the bot asked for a numerical grade (between 1 and 10) and
310 a text explanation (that could be a simple thumb-up or thumb-down emoji). Telegram sent our bot information about each evaluation and we saved that information in our voice-grades database. Finally, our bot executed the *notify* script again, this time to notify the students that they have received grades.
315 For consulting the grades, the learner sent the /query command to our chatbot. The bot then presented all the evaluations received to that user (maximum 5). For storing the metadata associated to each voice recording we used a MySQL database. For programming the chatbot management system's notify and assignment scripts, we developed a custom application in PHP. For communicating
320 the chatbot with Telegram, we used a PHP Library for Telegram bots ³.

³<https://github.com/akalongman/php-telegram-bot>

3.3. Main objective

For our experiment, we designed and implemented a Telegram chatbot that allowed our students to easily answer exercises by recording their voices, and to evaluate other students voice productions. Our hypothesis is that through this system we can effectively improve both the typical learning and the p2p evaluation process of a MOOC essay. We also tried to answer the following research questions:

- Can students' motivation be influenced by asking them to interact with their smartphones, recording their voice, thus fostering their active-participation in a MOOC?
- If so, how can we characterize those voice recordings? How are they produced/recorded? How are they evaluated?
- If so, how many and what length of voice assignments should we ask students to produce in order to maximize their engagement?

For proving the hypothesis and answering the research questions, we conducted a near two months long voluntary experiment with 77 learners out of 314 registered in our sMOOC. After the experiment finished, an analysis of the results was conducted, both studying the recordings and evaluation interactions and collecting our learners opinions with a satisfaction survey.

4. Results

We divided our results analysis in two sections: quantitative analysis (number of questions, voice answers, evaluations assigned, evaluations completed, answer duration, grades assigned...) and qualitative analysis (based on a final optional survey that the learners completed).

4.1. Quantitative analysis

There were 6 challenges distributed during nearly two months (from 2016-11-20 to 2017-01-06) with different number of questions for each challenge. As Fig. 3 shows, the challenges were published in pairs (1-2, 3-4 and 5-6).

Of the 137 participants that interacted with the bot, 77 users recorded their
350 voice, totaling 737 voice files, distributed as follows:

As can be seen from the above, we started collecting answers from learners on
2016-11-25. Some previous activity shown is attributable to app testing. As each
challenge was published (depicted with vertical dashed lines) there were some
recording surges. We have highlighted these surges in three gray segments. Each
355 segment starts roughly on the same day as the challenge publication. Another
factor is involved, visible in some small peaks on dates near Christmas. It's very
likely that these peaks are attributable to messages published by the teachers
promoting our students to record themselves before the deadline and likely also
due to the time available because of holidays.

360 The number of answers per user chart (Fig. 4.a) follows a typical distribu-
tion, with a long right tail (many users that only answered a couple of voice
challenges). The mean is of 8.922 answers/user, median 7.0/user, max. 23, SD:
6.58).

In Fig. 4.b the results by user and number of recordings on each challenge
365 show that not all of the learners answered all the challenges, and that chal-
lenges 1 and 2 were the most answered. These students may have thought that
the technology was designed to always start from the beginning. But it is also
important to remark that the chatbot allowed participants to start the conver-
sation through Telegram in any challenge that they would choose by selecting
370 it.

Table 1 summarizes the participation numbers more clearly.

Surprisingly, there are some participants that took part in the last two chal-
lenges but not in the fourth one. The last (sixth) challenge has more recordings
than the previous two. When the participation is calculated in the last column
375 (number of recordings/ number of participants) it can be seen that challenge 1
was attempted by fewer students than other challenges, probably because some
students did not initially understand the use of the chatbot. During the chal-
lenges 2, 3 and 6 the number of questions per challenge are quite similar to the
participation number, so it is assumed that most students were able to answer.

Challenge	Number of questions	Number of answers	Number of recordings	Participation (recordings/answers)
1. Why create a sMOOC?	3+1(text)	77	227	2.95
2. Project Management	4	57	236	4.14
3. sMOOCs Ingredients: Methodology, Pedagogy and Actors	4	23	83	3.61
4. Resources and supports of a sMOOC	5	15	60	4.00
5. Communication Plan and Accessibility	3	17	51	3.00
6. sMOOC Evaluation	4	17	80	4.71
TOTAL:	24	206	737	3.58

Table 1: Summary description of each challenge, number of questions and participation.

380 The number of participants decreased after the second challenge, which seems that generally, the learners who did not quit after the second challenge finished the experience.

4.2. Voice challenges and evaluations

Each learner had to evaluate others' voice answers using the chatbot. Only 385 those that had recorded a voice production were selected as candidates to evaluate others' work. The bot periodically sent a message to each evaluator candidate, presenting them with some recordings to evaluate (between 1 and 5, randomly selected from each challenge). The recordings were anonymous, and due to the high number of participants, it was nearly impossible to figure out 390 which voice corresponded to each student (meaning that it was a highly anonymous evaluation process).

The evaluation assignment process yielded the numbers shown in Table 2.

Challenge	Difficulty of the challenges (mode)	Number of evaluators ⁴	Number of learners evaluated	Number of recordings to evaluate ⁵	Percentage of recordings evaluated
1	1	75	49	78	30.8
2	2	52	34	52	36.5
3	2	15	7	15	53.3
4	2	13	7	12	50
5	1	12	7	13	30.8
6	1	4	3	4	0
TOTAL:	-	-	-	174	33.6

Table 2: Description of the challenges, the mode of the level of difficulty of the challenges, (expressed in 0 when the answer is almost instantaneous, 1 when requires a bit autonomously thinking and 2 when requires a deeper analysis and some consultation), and the number of evaluators, students evaluated and records done.

The previous two tables show that even though learners are willing to record their voices it is progressively difficult for them to evaluate each other's recordings. In fact, the number of recordings that were effectively evaluated decreased as the experiment went on.

When evaluating a recording, evaluators were presented with an audio file

⁴Number of distinct evaluators that will evaluate the recordings for the challenge. This number should be equal (ideally) or less than the number of learners who answered from Table 1. However, the evaluation assignment algorithm was applied only once, when the last challenge finished. We wanted to meet some restrictions: 1) each evaluator should have at least 1 and at most 5 assignments, 2) for evaluating, each evaluator had to record the same question that he/she was assigned to evaluate, 3) each question of each challenge had to have a representation in the number of answers assigned to be evaluated

⁵When a specific recording can be evaluated by two (or more) people it counts as two (or more)

that they had to listening to and two additional questions: the first one, asking for a numerical grade (between 1 and 10) for evaluating the voice production and, the other one, asking for a text comment. For those not inclined to add a text comment, we also accepted an emoji icon, suggesting a simple thumb-down or thumb-up as a possible outcome of the evaluation.

Challenge	# of recordings evaluated	Mean of grades	Min/Max	% of text comments	% of emojis
1	24	7	1-10	33.3%	66.6%
2	19	6.42	1-10	31.5%	68.5%
3	8	7.25	5-10	37.5%	62.5%
4	6	8.5	7-10	16.7%	83.3%
5	4	8.75	8-10	25%	75%

Table 3: Number of recorded answers with the grade of each one and the preference of correction by graphic or text.

As shown, learners are not prone to elaborate their gradings (only 19 out of 61 evaluations, 31%)

4.3. Assignment algorithm

The assignment algorithm that explains the numbers of Table 2 and Table 3 requires a more detailed explanation. Let's suppose that there are A answers to assign. These answers are generated due to different questions and challenges. Now, in order to assign these answers between E evaluators there are some restrictions: at most, each evaluator should have five assignments and at least one. Moreover, each evaluator can only grade an answer if he/she has previously answered that same question. Finally, there are no auto-evaluations allowed.

Those four restrictions can be satisfied using different approaches. For instance, choosing answers to be allocated ordered by creation date (first the older ones, that probably might be answers from the two or three challenges. Using

this approach we could meet the conditions and leave the last challenges without any representation (could be no answers assigned for evaluating from those challenges). The assigning strategy could be the opposite (assign first the newest answers), leading to a situation where no answers from the first challenges are
420 assigned to be evaluated. A random assigning algorithm could lead to some challenges over and under represented.

In our case, a fair algorithm was chosen, where each question from each challenge should at least have one evaluator assigned for grading. We are aware of the limitations of the algorithm and agree that in future iterations of the
425 course, further attention to this issue should be applied.

Fig. 5 summarizes graphically the assigning process. Three learners are represented. The first one (Learner1, colored as red) has answered only to questions of challenge 1: one recording for Q1, Q2 and Q3 and 3 recordings for Q4. Similarly, Learner2 (green) and Learner3 (blue) have also answered
430 the same questions but repeating only an answer for Q3 (Learner2) and no repeated attempts for Learner3. The peer to peer assignments are allocated as follows: Learner1 has to evaluate Q1/R1.1 and Q3/R3.2 of Learner2 and R3.1 of Learner3. This assignment is possible because Learner1 has herself answered those questions. Other assignments are colored with the corresponding evaluator
435 color.

4.4. *Difficulty and Length of the answers*

There is a preference of submitting short answers (Fig. 6.a). The answers of less than 30 seconds encompass 80% of the total answers, and more than 150 interventions last less than 10 seconds. A detail of these short answers (Fig 6.b)
440 showed that some of them could be due to errors with technology (less than 5 seconds) or to interrupted short attempts.

The chatbot suggested that any voice answer should have a duration no longer than 1 minute, however, it allowed longer answers. The length of the answers may be related to the difficulty of the students to answer, so a detailed
445 analysis follows, first as a general view and then aggregated by challenge.

In Fig. 6.a, we have created bins of 10 seconds that showing the number of recordings according to their length.

The longest recording last for 130 seconds (2'10"), the shortest last for 1 second (Fig 6.a). Taking only answers longer than 10 seconds, the mean is
450 34.36 with a SD=16.73. The boxplot in Fig. 6.c shows the distribution of those values (more than 75% of the recordings are between 11 and 46 seconds), pinpointing clear outliers.

Fig. 6.d shows the recording duration boxplot for each challenge. Logically, the challenge 4 has a taller third percentile due to the fact that it has one
455 question more than the others.

We wanted to analyze how many recordings were shorter than 10 seconds. This number likely reflects hesitant users. The number of short recordings can tell us how many users started the exercise but somehow, did not finish the recording (and usually, tried again).

460 As Fig. 6.b shows, there are a lot (243) of recording intents. Mean duration is 4.407 seconds, even though there are some larger ones (10 seconds maximum) and even some intents below 2 seconds.

4.5. Qualitative analysis

As mentioned, a final optional survey was circulated to our learners to evalu-
465 ate their satisfaction after using the chatbot and to receive feedback to improve in future editions of the MOOC and future versions of the chatbot.

With the goal of optimizing the tool for further cases, an opinion study was done among the students who took part in the experience. To accomplish it, a self-administered individual survey was developed from electronic media (Google
470 Forms), which guarantees anonymity as well as providing simple distribution and access. The link to take part in the survey was sent to students via the chatbot. The survey had 28 questions, of which 25 were closed questions. They were answered in a Likert type scale from 1 to 5, in which 1 meant completely disagree and 5 meant completely agree; three of them were open questions. The
475 survey collected the opinion of students in the following fields:

- Demographic features (age, gender, nationality)
- Rating of user friendliness of used technology.
- Rating of developed educative methodology.
- Overall rating of the experience.

480 Twenty respondents from ages between 24 and 67 years participated in the survey. There was a significant majority of women (75%) vs. men (25%). 75% of respondents live in Spain and the remaining 25% live in The Netherlands, Italy, Venezuela and Colombia. The survey feedback indicated that 63.2% of respondents had developed and worked on all the proposed challenges, so therefore
485 their opinion was relevant and significant. More than 75% of respondents completely agreed with the fact that the challenge solving system in Telegram was easy to use. They did not find it unnecessarily complex, nor uncomfortable and thought anyone could easily learn it. To the question of whether they thought the app was easy to learn by any person, 50% fully agreed and 40% agreed.
490 70% of surveyed people agreed that functions were correctly integrated. In conclusion, we can say that the user friendliness of used technology was reflected in a positive opinion. In the rating of developed educative methodology, 36% of surveyed people did not agree or disagree on the adaptation of the number of challenges. More than 40% of respondents agreed that the number of ques-
495 tions per challenge was correct and the time used to answer said challenges was adequate. It must be highlighted that there were a number of polled persons, 15%, that did not agree or disagree on the adaptation of challenges or the time used to answer said challenges. We also may found that 20% neither agreed nor disagreed with the integration of challenge resolution in a fiction narrative.
500 The percentage of people goes higher, to 30%, who neither agreed nor disagreed when it comes to rating Avatar Miguel, the Intern student. To sum up, though the educative methodology was appreciated, there were students who chose not to participate and some who did not fully embrace the new methods. Overall rating of the experience shows that 90% of respondents would like to use this

505 system in following courses.

Most valued by respondents	Least valued by respondents	Suggestions from respondents
Interaction	Occasional mistakes trying to understand the platform	Communication channels between participants
Simpleness	Improvisation when recording oral answers	Being able to re-record the audio
Flexibility	Void feeling in feedback	Shorter challenges
Ease	Not being able to interact with others. Just the bot	More precise questions
Immediacy	Mechanization of answers	Avoid using the code for access
Ubiquity	Challenges were not in order	Use of buttons
Possibility to save progress to continue later	Use of codes	Questions of different type
Possibility to answer via audio	Number of questions	

Table 4: Opinion of the participants in the experience divided into most and less value features and the suggestions offered.

Table 4 sums up the opinions of the participants in the experience. Having a look at the results, we have in mind that users appreciate the experience and consider the app simple, comfortable and easy to use, but also consider that it is improvable from a methodological point of view. The activity’s immersion
510 inside a narrative and adding an avatar as a learning guide has been well valued, but its rating does not shine as much as the value given to simpleness, ubiquity, flexibility and ease to use. The number of challenges and the number of questions per challenge should be revised. And, on the other hand, it would be convenient to improve the experience with some communication channel between users
515 through the Telegram app itself.

5. Discussion

After showing the results, this section is dedicated to analyse the initial set of research questions.

RQ1) Can students motivation be influenced by asking them to interact with their smartphones, recording their voice, thus fostering their active-participation in a MOOC?

Ninety percent (90%) of our students stated that they would like to repeat this experience of recording themselves using a chatbot to prove their knowledge in the future. This high number is probably due to several contributions (extracted again from the survey results): the tool is easy to use, flexible, provides immediate feedback and it can be used from anywhere, anytime -ubiquity-. This last point is specially interesting: users are not constrained to a web application for being able to participate. They can use their smartphone and start producing results with a simple click (without needing to log-in, selecting the actual exercise or needing a laptop to see it).

Familiarity and naturalness of the use of mobile devices in the learning process also contributes to the high acceptance rate (Briz-Ponce et al., 2016; So, 2016). The use of the same instrument that they are used to in other quotidian scopes, also helps to significantly increase the interaction among participants. Additionally, the prioritizing of an oral narrative over a written one in the chatbot increased participation (as expected (Morais, Albuquerque & Brandao, 2016; Silva, 2016; Stagg Peterson & Dwyer, 2016)) and the feeling of belong to a learning community in the sMOOC as well (Gallagher & Savage, 2016; Liyanagunawardena, Adams & Williams, 2013).

Anyway, as being a first experience with this new tool, there is space for improving. For this purpose it has been decided to release our chatbot system as an open source application. This way, the progressive improvement of the application will not only fall on the original authors but it could be distributed between other potential stakeholders (teachers, researchers, developers).

RQ2) If so, what features characterize those voice recordings? How are they

produced/recorded? How are they evaluated?

It is realized that the voice recording exercise is a demanding task. Probably, based on our enthusiasm with a new tool this issue was underestimated and we asked our students to produce 6 voice challenges (with up to 4 questions by
550 challenge). Results have shown us that asking for more than 2 voice challenges (with up to 4 questions by each one) was a bad idea.

On the other hand, the results show that the estimated duration of each answer was guessed correctly. Our chatbot proposed that each answer should not be longer than 1 minute and data show that students recorded, in general,
555 answers of 33-35 seconds. Could the time be reduced to 1 minute proposal and ask in exchange for more voice exercises? This is an open question that could be answered with more experimentation.

According to the grades scored, the quality of the voice answers was good or very good (with mean grades ranging from 6.42 to 8.75). This shows that
560 students were really engaged with the voice exercise. The duty was voluntary, and they did it because it was stimulating for them.

Regarding the evaluation, it was applied a simple assignment algorithm comprised of only three rules: a) each evaluator had to have, roughly, the same number of recordings assigned to evaluate, b) a learner could only become an
565 evaluator if he or she had sent, in turn, a voice-recording for be evaluated and c) auto-evaluations were not allowed. Even though these settings worked quite good, there were a lot of other possible criteria to use for exercise assigning.

For example, the popular LMS Moodle has a peer to peer exercise (called workshop) with other criteria for assignments: users can auto-evaluate themselves, teachers can also decide to divide the exercises so that each one receives
570 at least 3 evaluations (note that this is different to assign three exercises to each evaluator), or they can decide that learners are not forced to submit their answers in order to be able to become an evaluator. Asides from using the number of assignments as a criteria for allocating exercises to evaluators, in the future it should be a good exercise to have other options based on previous performance.
575 For example, assign exercises of "best" students only to other "best" students,

or on the contrary (in order to be used as a good practice examples) assign best-students productions to learners that are struggling with the subject.

RQ3 If so, how many and how long should be the voice assignments we ask
580 to produce in order to be satisfactory for our students?

The duration of the answers was adjusted to 1 minute, although in fact, most of them were shorter. Our students' results show that this 1 minute limit is a valid figure. On the other hand, the effort required to complete the questions was underestimated. Results show a steep decline of the answers after the second
585 challenge (each challenge had 4 questions). This experiment can be a warning to future practitioners of voice-based chatbot exercises: do not underestimate the effort required to record a voice message and do not ask more than 8 voice based 1 minute answers.

Another analysis to determine the correlation between the duration of the
590 answers and the grades received was done, finding a relatively strong correlation ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.0005$) within the number of answers shorter than 10 seconds. This is an expected result as short answers (less than 10 seconds) should all be negatively graded.

When the answers shorter than 10 seconds are dropped out, the correlation
595 between duration and grades shows still a moderated link ($r = 0.34$, $p < 0.02$). This could be mean that some students pay more attention to the duration of the answer than they should when grading positively an exercise. More research and a detailed analysis should be carried out in order to know if the results are conclusive.

600 **6. Conclusions**

This work describes a new method for peer-to-peer MOOC essays evaluation using voice recordings. For that aim, a chatbot in Telegram IM mobile app is used by means to perform new voice-recording assignments. As far as we know, this mobile-based chatbot experience is a unique and novel experience. From
605 the survey addressed to our students, we know that they especially valued the

interactivity, ease of use, ubiquity and the novelty of being able to record voice answers to exercises using their smartphone, anywhere, anytime. In addition, the inclusion of gamification elements - the one represented by Miguel as an avatar who facilitates and guides the immersion into the chatbot in Telegram
610 is highly appreciated by the participants of this experience. Nearly 90% of them (the learners) stated that they would like to use our chatbot in new courses. This number encouraged us to document our experience and share the source code of the chatbot application so other MOOC practitioners can leverage it.

There are some warnings that should be taken into account when using
615 chatbots with voice exercises: First, they should start lightly regarding the number of voice recording assignments. Our recommendation, according to our numbers is to not surpass two voice challenges each one comprising at most three or four questions. Otherwise, learners may burn out easily. Not bearing in mind these issues would complicate the attainment of our starting precept:
620 chatbots must make possible a narrative connection among participants and the avatar, on one hand, and among participants at the evaluation process, on the other.

Even though voice based essays can be a great resource in general and particularly well received by people with difficulties for writing assignments, it can
625 also be a sword of double edge when people with voice production difficulties take part in the course. It could be advisable to prepare a text-based version of the voice challenges for those cases.

Chatbots market is still in their infancy, especially when applied to education in general and higher education in particular. Yet, there are already
630 some experiments and reflections that show the potential of elearning related bots that will offer personalized user experiences, were each student will have access to personal teacher assistants or learning coaches in the form of bots ⁶. User-friendly chatbots, with voice integration are, in our opinion, part of the eLearning education that many of the over 2.5 billion people with at least one

⁶<https://chatbotsmagazine.com/chatbots-and-the-future-of-education>

635 messaging app installed will leverage. This article tried to shed some light about
how to use this kind of chatbots in a MOOC so others can replicate it on their
own courses.

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